

Ageing@Work

Smart, Personalized and Adaptive ICT Solutions for Active, Healthy and Productive Ageing with enhanced Workability

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Report on Data Aggregation Supporting Clinical Decisions

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Executive Summary

This deliverable is related to task T5.5 “Data Aggregation to support domain expert/clinical decisions”, whose main goal is to develop the necessary data aggregation strategies to support domain expert and clinical decision making. This includes the aggregation strategies themselves, as well as the visual analytics technologies that enable visualizing key aspects of the organization, thus offering informed decision making.

The main achievements outlined in this document are as follows:

- Formulation of a Data Aggregation Strategy that enables aggregated statistics and analytics regarding the ageing workforce.
- Development of a web-based Visual Analytics platform that enables organization managers to visualize at a glance organization schedule and cumulative figures regarding their workforce occupation.
- Development of a web-based clinical expert tool that enables OSH and clinical experts to visualize population statistics regarding various health-related aspects of the workforce, as well as individual data following full user consent.

The present deliverable is structured as follows: Section 1 presents a brief introduction to the deliverable and the related task T5.5. Section 2 discusses the developed data aggregation strategy, including details such as the aggregations employed and their rationale, privacy and data protection issues and implementation details. Section 3 discusses the development of the web-based Visual Analytics platform. Section 4 presents the development of the web-based Clinical Analytics platform. Section 5 concludes the deliverable.

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List of Terms and definitions

Abbreviation	Definition
API	Application Programming Interface
wVUM	Virtual Worker User Model
WP	Work Package
OSH	Occupational Safety and Health
MVC	Model-View-Controller
IOT	Internet of Things
IMEI	International Mobile Equipment Identifier

Table 1 Definitions

1. Introduction

1.1 Scope of the deliverable

The scope of this deliverable is to provide a detailed description of the work performed as part of T5.5 “Data Aggregation to support domain expert/clinical decisions”, which covers the development of the Ageing@Work Data Aggregation Layer, as well as the relevant user-facing Visual Analytics addressed to organization managers, as well as Occupational Safety and Health (OSH) and clinical experts. Looking at the big picture, the software tools outlined in this deliverable form a pipeline that enables the Ageing@Work system to “enable”, “produce” and “consume” data¹ at a large scale, with the aim of increasing awareness of management and OSH personnel, as to the opportunities and threats faced by the organization, with respect to the senior workforce. Within this scope, a first aim of this deliverable is to lay out the vision, principles and methodology by which the Data Aggregation Layer and Visual Analytics components have been realized. This includes review of related work, determination of the role and aims of the relevant software components, and translation thereof to concrete functional components. As part of this, the present deliverable includes a comprehensive presentation of the software architecture of the Data Aggregation Layer and the Visual Analytics components. Finally, this deliverable aims to fully describe the software implementation of the discussed software modules, including aspects such as model and database storage, interfaces and APIs, and validation and testing of the model.

1.2 Relation to other activities and deliverables

The present deliverable forms the main output of task T5.5 “Data Aggregation to support domain expert/clinical decisions” of the Ageing@Work project. The aims of this task stem from outputs that have been established in WP2, namely D2.1 and D2.6 “Requirements and Use Cases”, v1 and v2, and D2.3 and D2.8 “Ageing@Work System Architecture”, v1 and v2. Within WP5, the present deliverable is related to T5.2 “Worker Dashboard for Personalized Behavior and Workplace Analysis”, in that it implements the Data Aggregation Layer needed for Worker Dashboard functionality. In addition, the present deliverable is strongly related to D3.3 “Ergonomics and Work Orchestration Optimization Tools”, and relevant task T3.5, as far as the manager analytics and management tools are concerned. Finally, some of the outputs of the present deliverable, namely those related to remote collaboration in the manager platform, are linked to the activities of T6.4 “AR-Based Telepresence Tool for Remote Collaboration”.

1.3 Structure of the deliverable

The deliverable is structured as follows: Section 2 discusses the Data Aggregation Layer, starting from the definition of available data, establishing the necessary abstractions and aggregation requirements, and moving on to the design of the API endpoint implementations, and presentation of a concise table with all available API endpoints. Section 3 discusses the Visual Analytics Platform for organization managers. This includes firstly a brief presentation of workforce analytics state of art, and then the presentation of three main modules, which are presented to the user as views in a web-based application, namely the

Workforce Management View, the Visual Analytics View and the Workforce Interaction View. Section 4 discusses the Visual Analytics Platform that is targeted to OSH and clinical experts. In this section the concept, design and architecture of the application are presented, and subsequently a brief discussion on the implementation follows. Section 5 concludes the deliverable.

2. The Ageing@Work Data Aggregation Strategy

2.1 Introduction

In a broad sense, data aggregation refers to the practice of gathering data from databases and summarizing it in accordance with serving an intended purpose². In the context of Ageing@Work, we are faced with the challenge of enabling functionality of a series of user-facing modules, including the Ageing@Work mobile app, avatar, manager and clinical platform and others, while making use of a centralized consolidated data store, and in such a way that respects the privacy of the users, and is in accordance with established rules and legislation (e.g. GDPR). To address this need, Ageing@Work incorporates a data aggregation layer that takes on the role of aggregating and abstracting stored data, and making them available through a series of API endpoints. The data aggregation layer supports several different types of aggregations (summation, averaging, cardinality), and filtering of data based on time periods and other significant fields.

In this section, we begin in subsection 2.1 by taking a look at the definitions of the available data in the store, as well as the data consumers, that form the basis of the defined data aggregation functions. Subsequently, subsection 2.2 discusses the actual aggregation functions, parameters, and associated API endpoints. Finally, subsection 2.3 discusses aspects of handling of sensitive personal data, including aspects of anonymization and privacy protection.

2.2 Definitions of Available Data

In this section a brief overview of categories of data that are being aggregated is provided. Aggregated data fall into two broad categories: Individual worker data and workforce-aggregated data. Individual data serve user-facing modules, such as the Ageing@Work Mobile App. On the other hand, workforce-aggregated data are used to feed the Manager and OSH and clinical experts platforms.

2.2.1 Individual Data Aggregations

With respect to individual data aggregations, we distinguish the following categories:

- **Activity events:** Corresponds to events identifying user activities and the duration that the activity has been performed. Valid categories are 'walking', 'still', 'running', 'in_vehicle', 'on_bicycle', 'on_foot', 'tilting' and 'unknown'
- **Location events:** Corresponds to events identifying categories of location visited by the user, and their duration of stay. Available location categories are 'accommodation', 'automotive', 'business', 'social', 'education', 'health', 'landuse', 'publicservice', 'settlements', 'shop', 'sport', 'cultural', 'transport', 'workplace', 'home', 'friends', 'family', 'leisure' and 'unknown'.

- **Steps:** Corresponds to data identifying the total number of steps the user has performed
- **Breaks:** Corresponds to data identifying the total number of breaks from work a user has performed.
- **Sleep:** Corresponds to data identifying the total duration of different phases of sleep for a user
- **Leisure:** Corresponds to data identifying leisure activities for a user
- **Mental:** Corresponds to data identifying the mental wellbeing for a user. The data result from Mood Zoom questionnaire³ answers, and fall under the following categories: (1) anxious, (2) elated, (3) sad, (4) angry, (5) irritable, and (6) energetic, while the responses are recorded in a 1-7 Likert scale
- **Questionnaire:** Corresponds to aggregated data resulting from questionnaires that the user has responded to.

The above data categories refer to individual users of the Ageing@Work system. In general, as most of the data refer to time series, the provided interface needs to provide some form of time-based selection functionality. In addition, some of the data are related to categorical data, where recorded data are time points with associated categories. These types of data require an additional possibility to filter returned categories, in addition to time period.

2.2.2 Workforce-Aggregated Data

Workforce-aggregated data serve mainly to support the manager platform analytics views. As such, the necessary aggregations have been defined in accordance with this goal. In particular, the data aggregation endpoints support the following aggregation categories:

- **Daily workforce status:** Corresponds to data indicating the participation of each worker in the daily shift schedule as assigned to shift, working remotely or having a day off
- **Working remotely per age group:** Corresponds to data identifying the percentages of workers that engage in remote work, divided by age group.
- **Skills distribution per age group:** Corresponds to data indicating the distribution of skills in each age group in the organization.

The above data aggregation categories are filtered by time interval, in a similar fashion as the individual data aggregations.

2.3 Data Selection and Aggregation API

Based on the established aggregation requirements as outlined in the previous subsections, the corresponding data filtering and aggregation API has been established. In this subsection firstly the structure of the endpoints is briefly discussed, and subsequently an overview of each aggregation endpoint is presented.

2.3.1 API Endpoint Structure

To better manage the wealth of available endpoints, a common architecture has been established, which follows REST API practices⁴. The endpoint implementation follows a common structure as outlined in Figure 1. Following reception of the user request, the parameters related to aggregation and data filtering are derived and checked for consistency. Then, the SQL query is formulated and the call to the store is performed. The returned data are formatted according to the expected format by the endpoint and returned.

Figure 1 Flow Diagram for Data Aggregation API Endpoints

The Ageing@Work API, including the Data Aggregation API, has been developed using established OpenAPI tools, which enable a consistent development methodology and, in addition, offer a series of benefits, such as well-formatted API documentation pages (Figure 2).

Figure 2 Documentation page of the Ageing@Work API which includes Data Aggregation endpoints, in accordance with OpenAPI specification

2.3.2 List of Individual API Endpoints

The following table provides an overview of available individual worker aggregation API Endpoints. The table has been written in a simplified form compared to the full API specification for succinctness.

Table 2 Individual API Data Aggregation Endpoints

Endpoint	URL	Parameters	Aggregation Type	Response
Activity Events	/activity_events/	{activity_category} {from} {to}	Summation	Array of activity_category:duration elements
Location events	/location_events/	{from} {to}	Summation	Array of location_category:duration elements
Location events (category)	/location_events/	{location_category} {from} {to}	Summation	Array of duration elements
Steps	/steps/	{from} {to}	Summation	Array of steps and distance elements
Breaks	/breaks/	{from} {to}	Summation	Sum of breaks as integer
Sleep	/sleep/	{from} {to}	Summation	Array of sleep_stage:duration elements
Leisure	/leisure/	{from} {to}	Summation	Array of leisure_activity:duration elements
Mental wellbeing	/mental/	{from} {to}	Summation	Array of dictionaries with Mood Zoom keys and cumulative response values
Questionnaire	/questionnaire/	{category} {from} {to}	Summation	Array of dictionaries with questionnaire keys and cumulative responses

2.3.3 List of Workforce-Aggregated Data API Endpoints

Similarly to the previous subsection, Table 3 provides an overview of the workforce-aggregated API Endpoints. The table has been written in a simplified form compared to the full API specification for succinctness. The full API is available through accessing the OpenAPI-based Ageing@Work API documentation.

Table 3 Manager analytics platform API endpoints overview

URI	Description	Parameters	Response
/workforce/remote_workers/from/{from}/to/{to}	Get remote worker distribution by age group	from, to	Dictionary of status per age group

/workforce/skills	Get worker skills distribution by age group	-	Dictionary of skills (available/total) per age group
/workforce/distribution/from/{from}/to/{to}	Get weekly worker status and shift assignment data	from, to	Dictionary of shift assignments per day and per shift

3. Visual Analytics Platform for Organization Managers

3.1 Introduction

This section discusses the Manager Platform that is proposed by Ageing@Work and is targeted to support organization managers in carrying out the management of the workforce. The platform has been designed to provide a comprehensive overview of the organization workforce, focusing on aspects related to workability and efficiency. The platform enables managers to address all work and schedule-related aspects of the workforce and organization schedule, and provides the necessary tools to both efficiently summarize all workability aspects, as well as the necessary tools to support decisions related to scheduling. The platform incorporates tools to address the specific issues faced by the ageing workforce; for instance, the decision support engine that supports workforce scheduling takes into account particular aspects of the ageing workforce's needs, such as opportunities to work remotely using AR collaboration tools, or the frequency of health-related days off that may be required. Similarly, the visual analytics tools offer an overview of the state of the organization workforce, enabling insights that have the potential to lead to better decision making.

3.2 A brief overview of Management Analytics

It is commonly agreed upon that the effective management of workforce is an important aspect in any organization and has the potential to empower the workforce if performed in an informed manner. Visual analytics offer the potential to support decision making by offering insights into the organization's workforce skills, competencies, needs, and professional development⁵, so as to lead a more productive and engaging work environment. In relation to the goals of Ageing@Work, it has been reported in literature that this is particularly important for senior workers who contribute to the organization significantly through their extensive experience and knowledge⁶, therefore the alignment with Ageing@Work project goals is clear. Furthermore, specifically with respect to organization and decision making, the importance of insights in managing of the workforce skills and talents has been highlighted in literature, in particular with respect to the value of visualization and analytics tools⁷. Management of talent in the workforce has been a prominent category where analytics and visualization have been applied, in one instance leveraging monthly reports to track employee performance and engagement over time⁸. Elsewhere, the importance of multi-attribute decision making has been highlighted, and towards gaining relevant insights a visual analytics platform comprising multiple views towards workforce skills, productivity, contribution and further details has been developed⁹.

Through the aforementioned analysis, we may identify a number of points that indicate the potential for further research. First, and in relation with Ageing@Work project objectives, the availability of analytics and management tools that take into account the ageing workforce issue, and in relation to that the uneven distribution of knowledge over that span of the workforce age, is a significant aspect that needs addressing. Even more so, as the abundance of knowledge-based work positions in combination with

ageing workforce render organization knowledge a valuable resource. Second, tools offering data analysis often come separate from tools enabling managers to act, which creates a barrier between insight acquisition and action. Thus, there is an opportunity for a tool that unifies these two aspects, with an expected improvement in decision making overall.

3.3 Concept, Design and Architecture

The Ageing@Work Manager Platform forms a comprehensive tool to enable organization managers to effectively gain insights, manage and interact with the organization workforce. These three activities in fact form the three pillars on which the platform is based: Manage – Analyze/Visualize – Interact. They form three discrete main views, which implement the corresponding functionality. Managing of the workforce is implemented in a view that focuses on workforce scheduling and task assignment, where the manager is able to intervene on organization schedule as required, and is supported by an optimizing decision support system, providing scheduling suggestions. Analysis and Visualization forms a view that allows managers to gain insights regarding their workforce, through advanced visualization and analytics, which the managers may interact with to dig into specifics regarding the managed workforce. Finally, Interaction is a view that enables managers to view, examine and respond to requests made by workers, with respect to their schedule and task assignments, offering managers an informative summary of the post-action impact at the time of the action, therefore streamlining the decision making process.

The main idea behind the Manager Platform is to enable managers to gain deep insight on their workforce status, and, on the other hand, to make it easy for them to make changes to the organization schedule, while carrying the insight-generating content throughout the platform as much as possible. In this sense, the Visual Analytics embedded in the manager platform support the Management and Interaction views, as is demonstrated in the following Figure.

Figure 3 Structure and relationships of the Manager Platform user-facing components (views)

The overall software architecture of the Ageing@Work data aggregation system is based on the MVC design pattern¹⁰. The user-facing part of the platform is a web based UI that forms the view part of the system. The API forms the controller layer, and the combined database infrastructure used in Ageing@Work forms the model layer. In particular, the model layer includes the vWUM, workspace model

and scheduling database. Due to the MVC architecture, it is possible to aggregate data from multiple store sources while abstracting the complexity associated from the API consumer.

Figure 4 Architecture of the Ageing@Work Data Aggregation system, including the Manager platform

3.3.1 Workforce Scheduling Module

The Workforce Scheduling tool forms an essential part of the Ageing@Work Manager Platform with the main functionality to highlight to facility managers an overview of the workforce scheduling at any point in time and enable them to react to workforce requests (posted through the Ageing@Work mobile app), and to modify the schedule if required. The visualization tool relies on aggregated data coming from the Ageing@Work central repository, where worker shift information is stored. In addition, the visualization tool indirectly interfaces with the job orchestration tool (through the centralized store), to enable the latter to react to changes introduced by managers, as well as to evaluate the feasibility of schedule following a change.

The workforce scheduling visualization tool offers a number of different views towards the management of the workforce schedule.

Tasks	Morning	Evening	Night	Morning	Evening	Night	Morning	Evening	Night	Morning
	Monday, September 21st 2020			Tuesday, September 22nd 2020			Wednesday, September 23rd 2020			Thursday
drilling	Bob									
drilling		Maria								
transporting						Jurgen				
excavating				Bob						
excavating					Maria					
blasting									Susan	
drilling							Bob			
drilling										
machine_maintenance										
transporting										
excavating										Bob
blasting										
excavating										
blasting										
drilling										
transporting										
machine maintenance										

Figure 5 Ageing@work workforce scheduling tool, view of worker/task assignments

The first view is the Task-Shift table, which offers a Gantt chart-type visualization of the weekly tasks allocated in each shift, as well as the assignments to individual workers (Figure 5). Another view is the Weekly Shift view, which offers a better overview of worker status for each shift. In this view, columns represent shifts grouped by days, and rows represent individual workers. Through the use of clear visual indicators (Figure 6), different states can be visualized (Figure 7).

Figure 6 Schedule symbols for each different worker state in the weekly schedule

In addition to the worker/task assignment overview, by hovering over the table cells the manager is able to obtain additional information regarding the particular assignment, such as the task being assigned, the state of the task etc.

Figure 7 Ageing@Work Workforce scheduling tool mockup, weekly shift view

3.3.2 Workforce Visualization and Analytics Module

The Workforce Visualization and Analytics module is the second essential component of the Ageing@Work Manager Platform, enabling managers to obtain key insights into their workforce and workforce schedule, through the use of Visual Analytics dashboards. The Visualization and Analytics module comprises three main analytics dashboards, each dedicated to highlighting a different aspect of the workforce, among which the weekly workforce availability, the skills availability per age group, and the remote work per age group.

The weekly workforce availability (Figure 8) reveals the distribution of the workforce on a daily and shift basis, dividing the workforce among those that are actively involved in a task, those that are involved through remote collaboration, and those that are on leave or unavailable. Through this view, the manager

can get informed regarding the availability of workers on a particular shift, thus gaining insights on the potential to redistribute tasks or workers, in the case of an unexpected event or request.

Figure 8 Weekly Workforce Availability Graph mockup

The skills availability per age group (Figure 9) reveals the skills distribution in the organization, and enables the manager to assess the level of skill transfer from the experienced, senior workers to the younger generation. Through the insight offered by this view, it is possible for the manager to better organize remote collaboration sessions, and initiate knowledge transfer through e.g. targeted training events etc. Remote collaboration can improve the acceptance of mobile app suggestions by senior workers, through allowing more flexibility in terms of time, and can also improve knowledge transfer throughout the organization. Through the cumulative skills column on the right, it is possible to detect if a skill is in shortage, and compensate for that, for instance by letting senior workers possessing the skill to work remotely and assist more in-situ workers in achieving the task.

Skills Availability / Age Group					
	20-30	30-40	40-50	50+	Coverage
Skill A	0/5	3/5	3/5	3/3	9/6
Skill B	0/3	0/9	4/6	4/4	8/5
Skill C	1/7	2/5	2/5	6/7	11/13
Skill D	2/4	1/7	5/5	3/3	11/8
Skill E	0/2	2/5	5/5	5/7	12/15

Figure 9 Skills availability per age group mockup graph

Finally, the remote work per age group view (Figure 10) reveals the distribution of workers making use of remote collaboration per age group. This view enables managers to verify the percentage of workers working in remote collaboration, in order to pinpoint potential understaffing issues, and to evaluate the contribution of senior workers in organization knowledge sharing via remote collaboration.

Figure 10 Remote worker distribution per age group mockup graph

shows the manager platform with the analytics dashboard that includes the modules discussed in this section.

Figure 11 Manager view with visual analytics, integrated into the Manager Platform

3.3.3 Workforce Interaction Module

The workforce interaction module is responsible for enabling workers to submit requests to the managers and, correspondingly, for the managers to evaluate these requests and respond. The manager is able to visualize the worker requests in a calendar view, and view their status (Approved, Declined, Pending). Selecting a request, a dialog to manage the request appears, which enables the manager to respond to the worker's request. In addition, a comment visible to the worker can be supplied.

Figure 12 Worker interaction module dialog allowing managers to respond to worker requests.

Following the manager's response, the facility schedule is adjusted to account for the change in worker availability (Figure 12).

3.4 Implementation

The Visual Analytics Platform for Managers is implemented as a web app running PHP 7.0 with the Laravel framework on the backend, and Angular on the frontend. As part of the platform development, a comprehensive API has been created and documented, using the OpenAPI specification. As such, all data aggregation functionality related to the manager platform is available as a concise set of API endpoints.

4. Visual Analytics Platform for OSH and Clinical Experts

4.1 Description

The A@W Clinical Platform accommodates the functionality and visualization capabilities for OSH/clinical experts to overview workers' collected health-related data (e.g., aggregated over a selected period of time), and therefore enable them to take informed decisions. Demonstrations of the clinical platform functionality have been published in YouTube^{1,2,3}.

Figure 13 Clinical Platform communication overview

All the different data sources, from third party or built-in data collection, can be overviewed and visualized per category with graphs. In this context, the Clinical Platform receives from the worker's Virtual User Model (VUM) user data, such as demographics, behavioral and activity data, as detailed in D3.2 "Dynamic Virtual Worker and Workplace Models". In addition, the platform enables the registration of medical IoT devices (blood pressure monitor device, weight scale) and environmental sensors for monitoring temperature and humidity. Furthermore, there are tools for the healthcare experts to include new questionnaires and demographic questions for the application's enrollment procedure. Finally, authorized clients, according to their role (e.g., clinical expert), can overview user data and communicate with them

¹ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=GP-7Jwo7_6A

² <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=xcp0uXpyflc>

³ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=RQxpxpEO7IQ>

after the workers have provided their consent. Figure 13 demonstrates the communication capabilities of the platform with other devices and A@W components.

The backend of the Clinical Platform was built using NodeJs/Express because it offers great scalability and fast preprocessing with event-based modeling. The Clinical Platform has direct access to the VUM database, but additionally encapsulates a different database for medical data, such as those derived from medical IoT devices. The Clinical Platform supports the HL7/FHIR protocol for the representation of stored data, thereby promoting interoperation with other HL7-compliant systems (such as Electronic Health Records).

4.2 Consent request

OSH/clinical experts can request worker’s consent to access their data and are granted access only after the approval of the worker (Figure 14). The workers can overview their provided consent forms, extend them or withdraw at any time (Figure 15). After the approval of the consent requests, the workers are added to the clinical expert’s patient list, and it is possible for the clinical expert to overview the worker’s data. Both the workers and the clinical experts share the same views as shown below in Section 4.3.

Figure 14 Clinical expert’s consent request received by worker

Figure 15 Worker can extend or remove previously accepted consent requests

4.3 Data overview

For each day, an overview of the collected worker’s data can be seen, containing information about Activities, Goals and Steps (Figure 16) or additional information such as Heartrate, Floors Climbed and Sleep (Figure 17) collected by 3rd party applications.

Figure 16 Ageing at work data daily overview

Figure 17 3rd party applications (Samsung Health & Google Fit) data overview

4.4 Data Aggregation

It is possible to overview the data in an aggregated manner grouped by hours, days, weeks, months and years (Figure 18-Figure 21). Hovering the mouse above the graph segments will also provide the exact values.

Figure 18 Steps per hour

Figure 19 Sleep duration per day

By having access to such behavioral data, clinical experts who have a proficient understanding of the unhealthy habits, can spot bad patterns and give advice to the workers. Having in their disposal information from both medical IOT devices as well as their activities within a day, medical experts could make informed decisions about the recommended plan of action. Furthermore, social aspects could derive from the data such as the location context that could help clinical experts spot possible issues worsening the mental wellbeing of the workers (e.g., is the worker spending time outside of home or work?).

Figure 20 Walking per week

Figure 21 Heart Rate data over a month's period

4.5 IOT device data

With this platform users can register their IoT devices (devices manufactured by Medisante are currently supported), such as smart-scales or Blood Glucose and Pressure Monitoring Systems, through the Medisante’s Eliot Hub cloud service by providing the devices IMEI (Figure 22 and Figure 23).

Figure 22 IOT device registration

The data being collected from these devices are being stored in a different database under the Health Level Seven protocol (HL7/FHIR) and can be accessed only through the clinical platform.

Table 4. Example of data derived from smart scale.

```

"component": [
  {
    "code": {
      "coding": [
        {
          "system": "http://loinc.org",
          "code": "3141-9",
          "display": "Weight Measured"
        }
      ],
      "text": "Weight Measured"
    },
    "valueQuantity": {
      "value": 101,
      "unit": "kg",
      "system": "http://unitsofmeasure.org",
      "code": "kg"
    }
  }
]

```


Figure 23 IOT data overview

4.6 Other functionalities

4.6.1 Direct Messages

The clinical platform also accommodates the functionality of a live chat (Figure 24). Workers can share information with their doctors, and the doctors can provide suggestions to further remind them to follow the recommended guidelines when they detect abnormalities or unhealthy habits.

Figure 24 Clinical Platform – Direct Messaging Functionality

4.6.2 Workplace Environment

Everyone can overview the IOT sensors installed within the workplace environment. Information about

Figure 25 Environmental monitoring with temperature and illuminance sensors

the temperature, humidity, illuminance etc. can be overviewed as shown in Figure 25. Experts can examine the environment conditions and suggest changes to the managers if something should be improved.

4.6.3 Questionnaire creation tool

Finally, within the dashboard of the manager’s account it is possible to create new questionnaires or edit/remove previously created ones (Figure 26 and Figure 27). These questionnaire templates are retrieved by the application and are presented to the workers in order for them to provide their answers and therefore assess their health status (e.g., PHQ-9 questionnaire for depression detection, Mood Zoom questionnaire for daily mood assessment, etc.). Once a questionnaire is created and enabled, then automatically it may be displayed within the application without the need of an application update.

Questionnaire list

[+ Add new](#) Search...

Actions	Questionnaire name	Is enabled	Last updated
	PHQ-9	true	
	Big Five Personality Test (50)	false	
	Big Five Inventory - 2 (30)	true	
	Mood Zoom	true	
	VUM Questionnaire Part 1	true	
	VUM Questionnaire Part 2	true	
	VUM Questionnaire Part 3	true	
	SF12 HEALTH SURVEY	true	
	COPSOQ (short version) Work related well-being	true	
	UTAUT Acceptability of the solution	false	

« 1 2 »

Figure 26 Available questionnaires

Questionnaire information ✓ Save

Select language: English

Questionnaire title: PHQ-9

Small description: (Patient Health Questionnaire-9)
Over the last 2 weeks, how often have you been bothered by any of the following?

Is enabled:

Questions overview +

Little interest or pleasure in doing things? ✓ □ ✖ ▲ ▼

- 1) Not at all
- 2) Several days
- 3) More than half the days
- 4) Nearly every day

Feeling down, depressed, or hopeless? ✓ □ ✖ ▲ ▼

- 1) Not at all
- 2) Several days
- 3) More than half the days
- 4) Nearly every day

Trouble falling or staying asleep, or sleeping too much? ✓ □ ✖ ▲ ▼

- 1) Not at all
- 2) Several days
- 3) More than half the days
- 4) Nearly every day

Feeling tired or having little energy? ✓ □ ✖ ▲ ▼

Figure 27 Creating new / Edit existing questionnaire

5. Conclusions

This report presented the results of T5.5 “Data Aggregation to Support Domain Expert/Clinical Decisions”. The deliverable has been divided into three sections, aligned with the three expected outcomes of the corresponding task, namely: The Ageing@Work Data Aggregation Layer, the Manager Platform, and the Clinical platform. In each of these sections, the corresponding component is introduced through presentation of related developments in literature, and a brief mention of its goals and design principles. Subsequently, a functional description follows, which aims to establish the functionality of each component, and its contribution towards the task goal.

The main achievement of T5.5 has been the development of a unified solution to support managers, domain experts for decision making, offering tools that allow on one hand to gain insight and on the other hand to manage the workforce. Towards this direction, it focuses, in alignment to the Ageing@Work project goals, to the management of the ageing workforce, promoting a fair treatment and better advantage of the deep experience and knowledge of senior workers, through better distribution of knowledge throughout the organization. At the same time, through the integration of clinical analytics, it enables OSH and clinical experts to take proactive measures to ensure the well-being and productivity of the workforce.

6. References

- ¹ Brands, K., & Holtzblatt, M. (2015). Business Analytics: Transforming the Role of Management Accountants. *Management Accounting Quarterly*, 16(3).
- ² Jesus, P., Baquero, C., & Almeida, P. S. (2014). A survey of distributed data aggregation algorithms. *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, 17(1), 381-404.
- ³ Tsanas, A., Saunders, K. E. A., Bilderbeck, A. C., Palmius, N., Osipov, M., Clifford, G. D., ... & De Vos, M. (2016). Daily longitudinal self-monitoring of mood variability in bipolar disorder and borderline personality disorder. *Journal of affective disorders*, 205, 225-233.
- ⁴ Mulloy, B. (2013). Web API design.
- ⁵ Araújo, J., & Pestana, G. (2017, April). Articulating Gamification and Visual Analytics as a Paradigm for Flexible Skills Management. In *World Conference on Information Systems and Technologies* (pp. 185-196). Springer, Cham.
- ⁶ Araújo, J., & Pestana, G. (2017). A framework for social well-being and skills management at the workplace. *International Journal of Information Management*, 37(6), 718-725.
- ⁷ McAfee, A., Brynjolfsson, E., Davenport, T. H., Patil, D. J., & Barton, D. (2012). Big data: the management revolution. *Harvard business review*, 90(10), 60-68.
- ⁸ Raguvir, S., & Babu, S. (2020, October). Enhance employee productivity using Talent analytics and Visualization. In *2020 International Conference on Data Analytics for Business and Industry: Way Towards a Sustainable Economy (ICDABI)* (pp. 1-5). IEEE.
- ⁹ Zhao, J., Karimzadeh, M., Snyder, L. S., Surakitbanharn, C., Qian, Z. C., & Ebert, D. S. (2019). Metricsvis: A visual analytics system for evaluating employee performance in public safety agencies. *IEEE transactions on visualization and computer graphics*, 26(1), 1193-1203.
- ¹⁰ Leff, A., & Rayfield, J. T. (2001, September). Web-application development using the model/view/controller design pattern. In *Proceedings fifth ieee international enterprise distributed object computing conference* (pp. 118-127). IEEE.